

CULTURE OF GLOBALIZATION AND TOLERANCE

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Abstract. *This article talks about the importance of the culture of tolerance in the process of globalization, the problems of harmony with national values and its solutions.*

Keywords: *Globalization process, national value, tolerance, democracy, global problem.*

Tolerance is a global manifestation (globally) of individuality based on tolerance, respect for different views, beliefs, world culture, acceptance and correct understanding of universal values, self-expression of a person.

Tolerance in this step refers to the level of awareness of people from universal cultural processes, problems of interest or concern to humanity, the knowledge of universal programs, projects, decisions adopted by international organizations such as the UN, UNESCO, UNICEF, their activity in their implementation. Awareness of universal cultural property, knowledge of teachings, discoveries, works that have left a unique mark on human history, participation in the preservation of immortal historical and cultural monuments is noted as the main tasks in the program and declaration of action in the field of peace culture adopted by the declaration of tolerance Princeps and the UN General Assembly (September 13, 1999). The principle of the UNESCO Charter of 16 November 1945, "the construction of the world into the moral and intellectual unity of mankind", expresses the main core of the activities of the UN and UNESCO. For example, the UN is tasked with maintaining international peace and desolation, equal rights and self-determination of peoples, solving international problems of an economic, social, cultural and humanitarian nature, coordinating the movement of Nations, states in the eorization of these goals [1, p. 4]. Or, as stated in the "international pact on economic, social and cultural rights" of the UN General Assembly (December 16, 1966), all peoples undertake to independently determine political, economic, socio-cultural development, participate in international cooperation, realize the rights and freedoms of their citizens, create a way of life in accordance with universal norms such as promotion of everyone in their profession, field of work, 19, 30]. At the same time they legally guarantee the formation of a culture of tolerance in the global stage. Of course, the accession to this international pact (non-accession) is the voluntary work of the states, but today this document is signed by all states, including the Republic of Uzbekistan. Our republic has joined more than 90 international conventions, pacts, treaties that serve to shape global cultural tolerance to this day, deepening international integration [4, p. 237].

An important sign of the culture of global tolerance is Interstate (Inter-ring, inter-regional, regional-inter-Republican) relations, that is, the formation of alliances, associations, joint programs, declarations, communiqués, acceptance of pacts, participation in the fight against environmental, demographic, health, education, human development, peace and tranquility on Earth, drug trafficking, prostitution, trafficking in persons, famine of universal importance. Thus, the culture of global tolerance of states is a cooperation aimed at preserving civilization, applying cultural-humanitarian ties, development, creating a universal legal space for equal use of cultural assets, transforming democracy, cultural pluralism, cultural Integralism into a condition of universal progress [2, p.2). 201].

Today, humanity is living to face about 13 thousand global problems. To solve them, states, peoples, nations are obliged to expand cooperation, associations, ties. It is difficult for a separate state, people, nation to solve both its own problems and the problems of the general public. Tolerance does not consist in the peaceful resolution of conflicts between two peoples, nations, differences, tolerance across the state is also important. Under the banner of democracy, the forceful absorption of their views on other nations, peoples, and even the establishment of a coalescent intervention (attack on the United States, England, Italy, France, and Iraq) threatens the decision-making of a culture of global tolerance. This is in fact the terrorism of states against the preservation of peace at the national and Planetary levels, free development of peoples in accordance with their historical basis. "Tolerance," the declaration of tolerance principles States, " is not indifference to empty coming, indulgence, or impropriety. Tolerance is an active relationship that is formed on the basis of universal law and recognition of the fundamental freedoms of a person. In no case can tolerance serve to justify aggression towards these core values; tolerance must also be shown by certain individuals, groups, and states" [5, p. 1].

The initiatives of young people in the Red Crescent Society, the movement for voluntarism that arose in Europe, the Asian Youth Forum "Mkhatma Gandhi-nonviolent progress", spread in India, the "Blue Party", among others, are serving the decision-making of global cultural tolerance. For example, Uzbekistan also established a program of the UNV (international voluntary association) in 1993, a section (center) of the "Averd" Association in all regions. In addition to foreign youth, students, artists, athletes of the Republic participate in the volunteer movement, the motto of the volunteer movement is "it is preferable that benef lived worked beminnat" – which helps to solve it positively, citing it.

Tolerance is becoming a world-wide source of unique feedback in the conscious life of humanity and the mentality of society. The current concept of tolerance appeared very soon and is gaining expression in the peoples of the whole country. In particular, the main place in its emergence and formation is occupied by the "declaration of tolerance principles" adopted at the General Conference of UNESCO in 1995. It is strictly followed by 185 countries of the world, including the Republic of Uzbekistan. So tolerance is the norm and value of civil society.

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